

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SUGGOSTOPEDIC APPROACH IN CHILDREN'S PLAY ACTIVITIES

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Annotation

This article will talk about the development of speech of preschool children using a suggestopedic approach. Raising preschool children as comprehensively developed, physically healthy, mentally mature and spiritually formed is one of the urgent tasks. This process is associated with the development of communication activities in children and, above all, with the presence of a need for communication. Speech development is necessary not only to introduce the child to the environment, but also to develop him in a general spiritual way. Suggestopedia is based on a way to strengthen the memory and speech of the educator. In preschool education, it is advisable to use mainly psychological, didactic and artistic methods of suggestopedia.

Keywords: suggestopedia, modern approach, psycho-corrective, teaching technologies, motivation, interactive training.

INTRODUCTION.

Public policy in the field of training qualified specialists implies the intellectual and spiritual-moral education of a person, the achievement of his manifestation as a comprehensively developed person. The implementation of this social requirement guarantees the right of each citizen to receive knowledge, to demonstrate creative abilities, to develop intellectually and to work in a specific professional direction.

Today, raising preschool children as comprehensively developed, physically healthy, mentally mature and spiritually formed is one of the urgent tasks. In order to effectively organize the educational activities of preschool educational organizations, a curriculum was introduced along with a number of resolutions and laws. The state requirements for children of preschool age and the introduction of the “first step” curriculum are improved in some way different from the previous programs, serving for the development of the child and full-fledged learning.

The establishment of development centers in pre-Matab educational organizations provides for the implementation of state requirements and the "first step" state curriculum. Work in centers is organized in such a way that it allows each child to develop most efficiently, taking into account his individual abilities, interests, level of activity.

MATERIALS and METHODS live in the constantly growing informatization of society , which contributes to modern development, they find dozens of ways to influence the human mind in order to remember the necessary information.

Self-management methods based on the mobilization of human memory reserves are widely recognized, therefore, in modern teaching technologies, it is recommended to introduce elements of Psycho-corrective training in order to optimize the psychological state, intensively remember the educational process.

The development of speech of preschool children is a complex psychological process, which does not consist only in imitating the speech heard by the child. This process is associated with the development of communication activities in children and, above all, with the presence of a need for communication. Speech development is necessary not only to introduce the child to the environment, but also to develop him in a general spiritual way.

One of the non-traditional methods of education in the development of children's speech in the early age period is suggestive-pedagogical methods. There

is evidence that more than a thousand years ago in China, Buddhist priests whispered religious texts in the ears of sleeping educators, and thus they memorized information in a dream.

Since sleep-state suggestopedia brings a certain passivity and submission to the will of the educator, the other side of suggestopedia, the process of self-hypnosis, attracts the most attention. suggestopedia is one of the most common methods of pedagogy .

It is known that the educator's original profession is to guide learning to achieve optimal results, based on an individual approach to each educator, his goal, ability, etc. As a result, when working in suggestive centers with its physiological characteristics, psychological and psychotherapeutic opportunities not only relieve stress, but also increase the attention of the Educator, his ability to work.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION for the first time this method began to be used in the study of foreign languages. If an educator in the traditional teaching process could memorize up to 20 words per session, the educator memorized up to 100 words when using the suggestopedia method.

Suggestopedia is based on a way to strengthen the memory and speech of the educator. G.K. According to lozanov's research, the normal state of consciousness and the corresponding structure are based on the expansion of the possibilities of memorizing educational material due to suggestive effects.

This technology is based on five principles:

- no compression;
- study without overwork;
- learning is based on cognitive interest;
- motivation;
- training is carried out in large blocks.

At the same time, certain patterns of human memory are taken into account:

everything that enters the human mind is remembered, but only what is important to the educator, what excites him; works according to a specific principle: interesting, very interesting, not interesting.

The main methods of suggestopedia are psychological, didactic and artistic. Psychological techniques are the art of linking thoughts and emotions ; it takes into account appearance, gestures and facial expressions. Didactic methods-globalization of educational material based on the topic under study. The educator must see the main, general, then all other details, see the general "picture" and then see what it consists of. This makes it possible to form a holistic view of the world in educators. Artistic style is the study of a new global topic in the conditions of modern equipment, video materials, realistic games.

When using the suggestopedia approach, already known forms and technologies of education such as interactive training, new technologies, Story training, etc. are used.

The structure of the concentration Suggestopedia training is slightly different from that of traditional training.

Thus, when educators work in centers, in the first session, all the main materials of the topic are considered, without focusing the attention of children on details, the material given to children must be prepared in advance for each educator, both on the board for teamwork and for individual work. Educators are allowed, if necessary, to write notes, clarify reference signals.

In the process of game activity, special achievements are made in the suggestive approach.

Play is one of the main forms of activity of preschool children, through which information is conveniently, easily remembered. The game is based on the task of creating an interest in all new, unknown, mysterious things. The game allows you to see everything even in simple things. The peculiarity of play training is that they become part of children's lives, they suggestopediate themselves thinking and

understanding in the world around them.

Games based on the approach of APPRECIATION Suggestopedia help to overcome the psychological barriers of the educator and stimulate the spontaneous and direct manifestation of the personality's capabilities. In such conditions, games teach to be organized and conscious during the pedagogical process, while creating an atmosphere of relaxation, agility, and there is no feeling of coercion, the material is imperceptibly mastered, highly remembered. After such training, the map is perceived as a "quick" reference tool, as an "assistant", depending on which you can repeat your knowledge without difficulty.

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